

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4 AND 5*

Compd. no.	R	M.p./ B.p.** °C	Yield %
4a	H	80–90/0.25	60
b	4-CH ₃	L	52
c	3-CH ₃	L	50
d	2-CH ₃	L	51
e	4-Cl	L	55
f	2-Cl	L	54
g	4-OCH ₃	L	56
h	2-OCH ₃	L	52
i	4-SCH ₃	L	57
j	4-C(CH ₃) ₃	L	58
k	4-NO ₂	L	55
l	2-NO ₂	L	53
m	2,4-Cl ₂	L	54
n	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	L	52
o	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	L	51
p	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	L	50
q	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	L	52
r	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂	L	51
s	3-CH ₃ -4-Cl	L	54
t	2,4,5-Cl ₃	L	56
u	2,3,5-(CH ₃) ₃	L	54
5a	H	170/0.25	60
b	4-CH ₃	L	58
c	3-CH ₃	L	64
d	2-CH ₃	L	62
e	4-Cl	L	66
f	2-Cl	L	61
g	4-SCH ₃	L	62
h	4-C(CH ₃) ₃	L	63
i	4-OCH ₃	L	60
j	2-OCH ₃	L	64
k	4-NO ₂	138	65
l	2-NO ₂	L	61
m	2,4-Cl ₂	L	64
n	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	L	62
o	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	L	65
p	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	L	62
q	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	L	61
r	Pentachloro	198–200	60
s	2,4,5-Cl ₃	106	62
t	2,3,5-(CH ₃) ₃	L	58

*All compounds gave satisfactory Cl analysis.

**L=liquid; purified by column chromatography.

stirred for 1 h. A mixture of phenol (0.1 mol) dissolved in benzene and triethylamine (20 g, 0.2 mol)

was added to the stirred solution dropwise. After filtering off the amine hydrochloride, the solvent was removed by distillation and the residual liquid was purified by column chromatography on acidic alumina. The purity was checked by tlc over silica gel using benzene-acetone (9 : 1) as irrigant. The physical and analytical data of 4 are given in Table 1 : 4a $\nu_{\max}$ 935 (P–O aliphatic), 1 190 (P–O–C aromatic) and 1 260 cm^{-1} (P=O); δ 3.80 (3H, d, J 12 Hz, OCH₃), 3.5 (2H, m, Cl–CH₂) and 2.5 (2H, m, P(O)CH₂).

O,O-Bisaryl-2-chloroethyl phosphonates (5a–t) :

A solution of phosphonyl dichloride (3; 18 g, 0.1 mol) in dry benzene was added to a cold (10–15°) solution of phenol (0.2 mol) in dry benzene (200 ml) containing dry triethylamine (0.2 mol) dropwise with stirring and further stirred for 3 h at room temperature. After filtering off the amine hydrochloride the solvent was removed by distillation. The residual liquid was purified by recrystallisation in the case of solids. In some cases column chromatography was carried out over silica gel. The purity was checked by tlc over silica gel using benzene-acetone (9 : 1) as irrigant. The physical and analytical data of 5 is given in Table 1 : 5a $\nu_{\max}$ 940 (P–O–C aliphatic), 1 185 (P–O–C aromatic) and 1 265 cm^{-1} (P=O); δ 3.7 (2H, m, Cl–CH₂) and 2.6 (2H, m, P(O)CH₂).

References

1. N. K. ROY and H. K. TANEJA, *Pesticide Res. J.*, 1990, 2, 157.
2. N. K. ROY and S. K. MUKERJEE, *Pesticide Sci.*, 1975, 6, 497; P. DUREJA, N. K. ROY and S. K. MUKERJEE, *Pesticide Sci.*, 1980, 11, 685; N. K. ROY, B. LALLJEE and S. BEDI, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1980, 12, 2995; K. VASU and N. K. ROY, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1983, 11, 2657.
3. Y. L. NENE and P. N. THAPLIYAL, "Fungicides in Plant Diseases Control", Oxford and IBH, New Delhi, 1979, p 413
4. A. M. KINNEAR and E. A. PERREN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3437